

VICTIMOLOGICAL PREVENTION OF OFFENSES CARRIED OUT BY CRIME PREVENTION SERVICES OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

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Abstract

The article discusses the victimological crime prevention activities carried out by the crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies, and offers proposals and recommendations for the more effective organization of this activity.

Key words: internal affairs bodies, crime prevention services, offenses, victimological crime prevention, measures.

In our country, the crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies play a unique role in ensuring the protection of human rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests, raising legal awareness and legal culture in society, strengthening the rule of law, implementing measures to identify, study, and eliminate the causes and conditions contributing to the commission of offenses, social rehabilitation and social adaptation of victims of offenses, individuals prone to committing offenses, those who have committed offenses, including previously convicted individuals and those released from places of detention, and reducing the risk of individuals and legal entities becoming victims of offenses, that is, in carrying out crime prevention.

Specifically, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Crime Prevention"[1] outlines the system of bodies and institutions that carry out and participate in crime prevention, their powers, and one of the bodies carrying out this activity is the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In the system of internal affairs bodies, the main and wide-ranging structure for crime prevention is the Crime Prevention Service of the Department of Public Safety of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, which coordinates the activities of crime prevention units of internal affairs bodies.

It can be said that crime prevention is a system of legal, social, organizational, and other measures for general, special, individual, and victimological crime prevention, used to preserve and strengthen law and order, identify and eliminate offenses, as well as identify and eliminate the causes of offenses and the conditions that contribute to them.

The main tasks of crime prevention are to ensure the protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of individuals, to raise legal awareness and legal culture in society, to strengthen the rule of law, as well as to form an intolerant attitude towards corruption, to identify, study, and take measures to eliminate the causes of offenses and the conditions that contribute to them, to ensure the social rehabilitation and social adaptation of victims of offenses, those prone to committing offenses, those who have committed offenses, including those previously convicted and released from places of imprisonment, to reduce the risk of individuals becoming victims of offenses, and to ensure cooperation and coordination between bodies and institutions directly implementing and participating in crime prevention[2].

In particular, the advantages of crime prevention include:

first, it is aimed at identifying and eliminating the roots and sources, causes and conditions of negative phenomena;

secondly, to have a preliminary impact on the chain of events that can cause significant damage to public relations protected by law;

thirdly, the ability to influence, eliminate, and weaken criminogenic factors at a time when they are only emerging and not yet firmly rooted, with minimal effort and costs;

fourth, humanity in relation to other areas in the system of law enforcement;

fifth, the ability to comprehensively apply economic, political, cultural, spiritual, legal, and other measures;

sixth, transparency, the participation of the general public, is manifested in its implementation based on the principles of relying on public opinion.[3]

It should be noted that today, ensuring law and order is becoming increasingly preventive,[4] and it is not an exaggeration to say that the role and significance of crime prevention activities in society is increasing. In carrying out this activity, the Department of Public Safety of the Ministry of Internal Affairs plays an important role in the prevention of offenses, and in their activities in the prevention of offenses, victimological prevention of offenses is of particular importance.

Prior to the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Crime Prevention," the concept of "victimological crime prevention" was introduced into law enforcement practice. According to this law, victimological prevention of offenses is the activity of the body or institution directly carrying out crime prevention to apply preventive measures aimed at reducing the risk of a specific person becoming a victim of a crime.

The goal of victimological crime prevention is to minimize the likelihood of victims by comprehensively studying the socio-legal relationships associated with the victimization of subjects of social relations, that is, to identify, eliminate, neutralize and reduce the impact of victimogenic factors, as well as to identify individuals with a high level of victimization, implement comprehensive protective and educational measures aimed at reducing their risk of victimization. In other words, victimological prevention is aimed at individuals prone to being victims of offenses, as well as at eliminating the factors that shape such a predisposition.

It should be noted that there are objective and subjective factors of victimization. Objective factors include the spiritually and physically weak, women, the elderly, young children, people with disabilities, and those of a passive nature (cowards, timid individuals). Subjective factors include: gullible people, the careless, the boastful (those who flaunt their wealth, material possessions, etc.), and we can note quarrelsome individuals.

It can be said that victimological prevention itself can also be carried out in general, specific, and individual forms[6]. In other words, although the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Offenses"[7] does not contain a separate approach to the types, forms, and methods of victimological prevention, theoretical provisions have been developed in this regard. It is precisely on the basis of these rules and procedures that victimological crime prevention can be studied by dividing it into the following types:

first, general victimological prevention;

second, individual victimological prevention;

third, special victimological prevention;

fourth, practical victimological prevention[8].

Each of the aforementioned preventive measures has its own characteristics and requires a responsible approach from the implementing subjects. In other words, for each preventive measure, it is advisable to follow these stages sequentially: preparation, direct implementation, analysis of results, and elimination of existing problems and shortcomings.

It should be noted that the types, methods, and forms of victimological crime prevention constitute the content of this activity. Knowledge in this area ensures the effective organization and implementation of victimological crime prevention. Furthermore, the formation of legal awareness and culture among citizens is one of the main directions of victimological prevention.

In the process of victimological prevention of offenses, the crime prevention services of the internal affairs bodies must conduct preventive measures in relation to victims of offenses in the territory where they serve, taking into account the individual and socio-psychological characteristics of the person. They should train the population, including victims of offenses, in methods of resolving disputes between individuals, take measures to identify and protect victims of offenses, establish specialized institutions providing assistance to victims of offenses, and develop and implement special comprehensive measures aimed at ensuring the physical and psychological safety of victims of offenses.

Additionally, in the process of victimological crime prevention, the crime prevention services of the internal affairs bodies should inform the victims of offenses about the methods and means of self-defense provided for by law, regularly monitor places (territories) where antisocial behavior is relatively frequent or where offenses often occur, provide legal education and training to the population by broadly disseminating information about necessary defense and extreme necessity in the event of an attack, establish trust hotlines, emergency communication lines, and rescue services under the bodies or institutions directly implementing crime prevention to obtain information about antisocial behavior, offenses being prepared, being committed or already committed. They should also organize public discussions of draft prevention programs and measures, create websites, blogs, and chats on the World Wide Web to identify and address problems and shortcomings in their implementation, and distribute electronic literature on modern methods of crime prevention. These measures will yield positive results

In conclusion, it can be said that in the process of implementing victimological crime prevention by the crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies, it is advisable to take the following measures: prevent the commission of offenses by raising legal awareness and culture of individuals and emphasizing the inevitability of responsibility for offenses; provide information to the general public about the social danger of offenses and offenders, as well as methods and means of committing offenses, to achieve self-protection; socially adapt and rehabilitate victims of offenses; morally correct individuals with antisocial behavior, those prone to committing offenses, and those who have already committed offenses; and implement measures to ensure personal and property safety of individuals with a high probability of victimization..

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